

Design, synthesis, characterization and evaluation of 1-aminomethyl-3-{4'-(4''-nitrobenzyloxy)benzoylhydrazono}-5/6-chloroindolin-2-ones

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Abstract : A new series of 1-aminomethyl-3-{4'-(4''-nitrobenzyloxy)benzoylhydrazono}-5/6-chloroindolin-2-ones (Mannich bases) have been synthesized and screened for their antifungal potential against human pathogenic fungi. The structures of the compounds have been elucidated with the help of elemental analysis and spectral data (IR, ¹H NMR and Mass).

Keywords : Indole-2,3-dione, Schiff base, Mannich base, aminomethylation, antifungal activity.

Introduction

Recently four review articles¹⁻⁴ have been published on the chemistry and biological potential of indole-2,3-diones. In the light of these reviews and in continuation of our work on biologically active heterocycles⁵⁻⁷, it was considered of interest to synthesise a new series of 1-aminomethyl-3-{4'-(4''-nitrobenzyloxy)benzoylhydrazono}-5/6-chloroindolin-2-ones (Mannich bases) and evaluate the compounds for their antifungal potential.

Results and discussion

4-(4'-Nitrobenzyloxy)benzoylhydrazine **2**⁸ was condensed with 5/6-chloroindole-2,3-diones and *N*-substituted-5/6-chloroindole-2,3-diones, in equimolar proportion to give 3-[4'-(4''-nitrobenzyloxy)benzoylhydrazono]-5/6-chloroindolin-2-ones **3a,b** and 1-substituted-3-[4'-(4''-nitrobenzyloxy)benzoylhydrazono]-5/6-chloroindolin-2-ones **4a,b-6a,b** (Schiff bases). Schiff bases **3a,b** on being subjected to aminomethylation with secondary amines in the presence of formaldehyde, gave 1-aminomethyl-3-{4'-(4''-nitrobenzyloxy)benzoylhydrazono}-5/6-chloroindolin-2-ones **7a,b-15a,b** (Mannich bases) (Scheme 1).

Antifungal activity :

All the compounds **3a,b-15a,b** were screened for their *in vitro* antifungal potential against human pathogenic fungi

Candida albicans (CA), *Cryptococcus neoformans* (CN), *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* (TM) and *Aspergillus fumigatus* (AF) using tube dilution method^{9,10} at a maximum concentration of 100 µg/mL in DMSO. The spore suspension of 10⁵ spores/mL was used for this purpose. The drug dilutions were made serially. The test was performed at 29 °C and Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) in µg/mL was recorded by visual observation after 24–72 h incubation. Suitable controls : broth control (without infection), growth control (with infection), solvent DMSO, drug controls (all test compounds) and ketoconazole (as standard drug) were set under identical conditions. The last tube with no apparent growth of organism represented the MIC of compound. Antifungal activity data are presented in Table 1. Schiff bases **3a** and **3b** (with unsubstituted 5- and 6-chloroindole-2,3-diones) were found to be inactive against the tested fungi while Schiff bases with 1-methyl-5- and 6-chloroindole-2,3-diones i.e. **4a** and **4b** showed MIC 6.25 and 12.5 µg/mL against TM and AF respectively just double to the standard drug ketoconazole. Schiff bases **5a,b** and **6a,b** with 1-ethyl and 1-acetyl-5- and 6-chloroindole-2,3-diones were also found active against TM and AF. Compounds **5a** and **6b** both showed MIC 12.5 µg/mL against both TM and AF whereas **6a** showed 6.25 and 12.5 µg/mL against

Scheme 1

both fungi, just double to the standard drug. Mannich bases **7a,b**, **8a,b**, **10a,b**, **11a,b**, **14a,b** and **15a** showed MIC 12.5 µg/mL against AF, double to ketoconazole hence showing good activity like that of Schiff bases. Similarly compounds **10a**, **11a** showed MIC 6.25 µg/mL against TM again good activity. Compounds **9a,b**, **12a,b**, **13a,b** showed MIC 25 µg/mL hence moderate activity against AF while **7a**, **8a**, **10b**, **11b**, **14a,b** and **15b** showed 25 µg/mL and were found moderately active against TM. Rest of the Mannich bases were found to be either inactive or very weakly active against other fungi. No Struc-

ture Activity Relationship (SAR) could be established since no clear cut change in trend of antifungal potential was seen neither in terms of position of chlorine in indole-2,3-diones and alkyl or acylsubstitution/aminomethyl group at 1 position in indole-2,3-diones.

Experimental

The melting points were determined in open capillary tubes in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer RX1 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR on Bruker DRX-300 spec-

Table 1. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration, MIC ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) of compounds against fungi

Compd.	<i>Candida albicans</i> (CA)	<i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i> (CN)	<i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i> (TM)	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> (AF)
3a	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
3b	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
4a	25	25	6.25	12.5
4b	> 100	50	6.25	12.5
5a	50	25	12.5	12.5
5b	> 100	50	25	25
6a	25	25	6.25	12.5
6b	> 100	50	12.5	12.5
7a	> 100	> 100	12.5	12.5
7b	12.5	12.5	25	12.5
8a	> 100	> 100	12.5	12.5
8b	25	25	25	12.5
9a	> 100	> 100	25	25
9b	> 100	> 100	25	25
10a	12.5	> 100	6.25	12.5
10b	> 100	25	12.5	12.5
11a	12.5	> 100	6.25	12.5
11b	> 100	25	12.5	12.5
12a	> 100	25	25	25
12b	> 100	> 100	25	25
13a	> 100	> 100	50	25
13b	> 100	> 100	25	25
14a	> 100	> 100	12.5	12.5
14b	> 100	> 100	12.5	12.5
15a	> 100	> 100	25	12.5
15b	25	25	12.5	> 100
Ketoconazole (Standard drug)	0.39	0.78	3.12	6.25

trometer. $\text{CDCl}_3/\text{DMSO}-d_6$ were used as solvent and TMS as internal reference. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ (ppm). Mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol-JMS-300 spectrometer. Elemental analysis data were obtained on Carlo Erba 1108 analyser. Homogeneity of the compounds was checked by TLC silica gel G plates and spots were located by exposure to iodine vapours.

3-[4'-(4''-Nitrobenzyloxy)benzoylhydrazono]-5-chloroindolin-2-one ($R_1 = \text{Cl}$, $R_2 = \text{H}$) **3a** :

A mixture of 4-(4'-nitrobenzyloxy)benzoylhydrazine **2** (0.01 mol) and 5-chloroindole-2,3-dione (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 mL) containing 2–3 drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 1 h and left overnight at RT. The

separated solid was filtered and washed with methanol. Yield 76%, m.p. > 250 °C; IR (cm^{-1}) : 3480, 3170 (NH), 1691 (CO), 1528, 1345 (NO_2), 1254 ($-\text{CH}_2\text{O}-$), 763 (C-Cl); MS (m/z) : 450 ($\text{M}^{+\bullet}$), 452 ($\text{M}+2$) (Found : C, 58.58; H, 3.27; N, 12.46. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{15}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}_5$: C, 58.61; H, 3.35; N, 12.43%); **3b** : ($R_1 = \text{H}$, $R_2 = \text{Cl}$) Yield 78%, m.p. > 250 °C (Found : C, 58.55; H, 3.30; N, 12.39. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{15}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}_5$: C, 58.61; H, 3.35; N, 12.43%).

Other Schiff bases **3b**, **4a,b-6a,b** were synthesized by similar methods using 6-chloroindole-2,3-dione and *N*-methyl, *N*-ethyl and *N*-acetyl-5/6-chloroindole-2,3-diones respectively.

1-Methyl-3-[4'-(4''-nitrobenzyloxy)benzoylhydrazono]-5-chloroindolin-2-one ($R_1 = Cl$, $R_2 = H$) **4a** :

Yield 86%; m.p. >250 °C; 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm : 2.63 (3H, s, Me), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.96–7.02 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.31 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 9.0 Hz), 7.66 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 8.7 Hz), 7.76 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.80 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 9.0 Hz), 8.01 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 8.7 Hz), 13.98 (1H, s, CONH); MS m/z : 464 ($M^{+\bullet}$), 466 ($M+2$) (Found : C, 59.36; H, 3.63; N, 11.96. Calcd. for C₂₃H₁₇ClN₄O₅ : C, 59.43; H, 3.69; N, 12.05%); **4b** : ($R_1 = H$, $R_2 = Cl$) Yield 67%, m.p. >250 °C (Found : C, 59.33; H, 3.63; N, 11.93. Calcd. for C₂₃H₁₇ClN₄O₅ : C, 59.43; H, 3.69; N, 12.05%).

1-Ethyl-3-[4'-(4''-nitrobenzyloxy)benzoylhydrazono]-5-chloroindolin-2-one ($R_1 = Cl$, $R_2 = H$) **5a** :

Yield 73%; m.p. >250 °C; 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm : 2.12–2.16 (3H, t, Me), 2.56–2.67 (2H, q, CH₂), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.88–6.99 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.37 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 9.0 Hz), 7.63 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 8.7 Hz), 7.81 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.98 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 9.0 Hz), 8.12 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 8.7 Hz), 13.98 (1H, s, CONH); MS m/z : 478 ($M^{+\bullet}$), 480 ($M+2$) (Found : C, 60.12; H, 3.93; N, 11.67. Calcd. for C₂₄H₁₉ClN₄O₅ : C, 60.19; H, 4.00; N, 11.70%); **5b** : ($R_1 = H$, $R_2 = Cl$) Yield 67%, m.p. 248–250 °C (Found : C, 60.13; H, 3.92; N, 11.64. Calcd. for C₂₄H₁₉ClN₄O₅ : C, 60.19; H, 4.00; N, 11.70%).

1-Acetyl-3-[4'-(4''-nitrobenzyloxy)benzoylhydrazono]-5-chloroindolin-2-one ($R_1 = Cl$, $R_2 = H$) **6a** :

Yield 66%; m.p. 246 °C; 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ ppm : 2.32 (3H, s, COMe), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.94–7.02 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.28 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 9.0 Hz), 7.65 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 8.7 Hz), 7.73 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.80 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 9.0 Hz), 8.01 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 8.7 Hz), 13.89 (1H, s, CONH); MS m/z : 504 ($M^{+\bullet}$), 506 ($M+2$) (Found : C, 58.42; H, 3.43; N, 11.33. Calcd. for C₂₄H₁₇ClN₄O₆ : C, 58.49; H, 3.48; N, 11.37%); **6b** : ($R_1 = H$, $R_2 = Cl$) Yield 76%, m.p. 220 °C (d) (Found : C, 58.41; H, 3.35; N, 11.30. Calcd. for C₂₄H₁₇ClN₄O₆ : C, 58.49; H, 3.48; N, 11.37%).

1-Morpholinomethyl-3-[4'-(4''-nitrobenzyloxy)benzoylhydrazono]-5-chloroindolin-2-one ($R_1 = Cl$, $R_2 = H$) **7a** :

To a suspension of **3a** (0.005 mol) in DMF, formalde-

hyde (0.5 mL, 37% aq. solution) and morpholine (0.005 mol) was added with vigorous stirring, warmed for 2 min on a water bath and left overnight at RT. The solid product thus obtained was filtered, washed with methanol, dried and purified by recrystallization from chloroform : pet. ether (60–80 °C) (1 : 1). Yield 74%, m.p. 212–214 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3480 (NH), 2804 (>N-CH₂-N<), 1683 (CO), 1529, 1349 (NO₂), 1253 (-CH₂O-), 1157 (-CH₂O-CH₂-), 758 (C-Cl); 1H NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm : 2.63–2.67 (4H, t, -CH₂-NCH₂-), 3.69–3.72 (4H, t, -CH₂-O-CH₂-), 4.50 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.77–6.89 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.31 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 9.0 Hz), 7.64 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 8.7 Hz), 7.86 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.98 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 9.0 Hz), 8.11 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 8.7 Hz), 13.77 (1H, s, CONH); MS m/z : 549 ($M^{+\bullet}$), 551 ($M+2$) (Found : C, 58.93; H, 4.34; N, 12.67. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₄ClN₅O₆ : C, 58.97; H, 4.40; N, 12.73%); **7b** : ($R_1 = H$, $R_2 = Cl$) Yield 74%, m.p. 220 °C (d) (Found : C, 58.90; H, 4.32; N, 12.70. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₄ClN₅O₆ : C, 58.97; H, 4.40; N, 12.73%).

Mannich bases **7b** and **8a,b-15a,b** were synthesized using same procedure and different secondary amines.

1-Piperidinomethyl-3-[4'-(4''-nitrobenzyloxy)benzoylhydrazono]-5-chloroindolin-2-one ($R_1 = Cl$, $R_2 = H$) **8a** :

Yield 68%, m.p. 216–218 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3456 (NH), 2853 (>N-CH₂-N<), 1686 (CO), 1521, 1349 (NO₂), 1250 (-CH₂O-), 770 (C-Cl); 1H NMR (CDCl₃) : 1.42–1.59 (6H, m, -CH₂CH₂CH₂-), 2.58–2.61 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 4.52 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.07–7.15 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.36 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 9.0 Hz), 7.60 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 8.7 Hz), 7.77 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.89 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 9.0 Hz), 8.00 (2H, d, Ar-H, J 8.7 Hz), 13.87 (1H, s, CONH); MS m/z : 547 ($M^{+\bullet}$), 549 ($M+2$) (Found : C, 61.32; H, 4.66; N, 12.67. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₆ClN₅O₅ : C, 61.37; H, 4.78; N, 12.78%); **8b** : ($R_1 = H$, $R_2 = Cl$) Yield 70%, m.p. 216 °C (d) (Found : C, 61.30; H, 4.70; N, 12.70. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₆ClN₅O₅ : C, 61.37; H, 4.78; N, 12.78%).

1-Pyrrolidinomethyl-3-[4'-(4''-nitrobenzyloxy)benzoylhydrazono]-5-chloroindolin-2-one ($R_1 = Cl$, $R_2 = H$) **9a** :

Yield 68%, m.p. 134–136 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3466 (NH), 2803 (>N-CH₂-N<), 1678 (CO), 1522, 1345 (NO₂),

1251 (-CH₂O-), 763 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 1.35–1.42 (4H, m, -CH₂CH₂-), 2.33–2.46 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 4.54 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.00–7.13 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.36 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 9.0 Hz), 7.60 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 8.7 Hz), 7.82 (1H, s, Ar-H), 8.06 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 9.0 Hz), 8.14 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 8.7 Hz), 13.83 (1H, s, CONH); MS *m/z* : 533 (M⁺•), 535 (M+2) (Found : C, 60.68; H, 4.46; N, 13.17. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₄ClN₅O₅ : C, 60.73; H, 4.53; N, 13.12%). **9b** : (R₁ = H, R₂ = Cl) Yield 67%, m.p. 220 °C (d) (Found : C, 60.67; H, 4.47; N, 13.06. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₄ClN₅O₅ : C, 60.73; H, 4.53; N, 13.12%).

1-N-Methylpiperazinomethyl-3-[4'-(4''-nitrobenzyloxy)-benzoylhydrazono]-5-chloroindolin-2-one (R₁ = Cl, R₂ = H) **10a** :

Yield 69%, m.p. 180–182 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 1.87 (3H, s, N-Me), 2.33–2.39 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 2.56–2.65 (4H, t, -CH₂-N(Me)-CH₂-), 4.55 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.85–6.99 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.11 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 9.0 Hz), 7.33 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 8.7 Hz), 7.59 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 9.0 Hz), 7.82 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.98 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 8.7 Hz), 14.00 (1H, s, CONH); MS *m/z* : 562 (M⁺•), 564 (M+2) (Found : C, 59.68; H, 4.78; N, 14.87. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₇ClN₆O₅ : C, 59.73; H, 4.83; N, 14.93%). **10b** : (R₁ = H, R₂ = Cl) Yield 56%, m.p. 192 °C (d) (Found : C, 59.69; H, 4.78; N, 14.88. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₇ClN₆O₅ : C, 59.73; H, 4.83; N, 14.93%).

1-N-Ethylpiperazinomethyl-3-[4'-(4''-nitrobenzyloxy)-benzoylhydrazono]-5-chloroindolin-2-one (R₁ = Cl, R₂ = H) **11a** :

Yield 69%, m.p. 180–182 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 1.87–1.92 (3H, t, Me), 2.00–2.09 (2H, q, -CH₂Me), 2.33–2.39 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 2.56–2.65 (4H, t, -CH₂-N(Et)-CH₂-), 4.55 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.88–6.99 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.09 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 9.0 Hz), 7.33 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 8.7 Hz), 7.60 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 9.0 Hz), 7.82 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.98 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 8.7 Hz), 14.00 (1H, s, CONH); MS *m/z* : 576 (M⁺•), 578 (M+2) (Found : C, 60.28; H, 4.98; N, 14.47. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₉ClN₆O₅ : C, 60.36; H, 5.07; N, 14.56%). **11b** : (R₁ = H, R₂ = Cl) Yield 56%, m.p. 198 °C (d) (Found : C, 60.30; H, 4.89; N, 14.47. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₉ClN₆O₅ : C, 60.36; H, 5.07; N, 14.56%).

1-N-Phenylpiperazinomethyl-3-[4'-(4''-nitrobenzyloxy)-benzoylhydrazono]-5-chloroindolin-2-one (R₁ = Cl, R₂ = H) **12a** :

Yield 60%, m.p. 220 °C (d); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3453 (NH), 2833 (>N-CH₂-N<), 1678 (CO), 1529, 1346 (NO₂), 1244 (-CH₂O-) 768 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 2.33–2.41 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 2.46–2.65 (4H, t, -CH₂-N(Ph)-CH₂-), 4.55 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.04–7.12 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.30 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.38 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 9.0 Hz), 7.48 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.51–7.55 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.65 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 8.7 Hz), 7.85 (1H, s, Ar-H), 8.00 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 9.0 Hz), 8.27 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 8.7 Hz), 13.90 (1H, s, CONH); MS *m/z* : 624 (M⁺•), 626 (M+2) (Found : C, 63.32; H, 4.56; N, 13.47. Calcd. for C₃₃H₂₉ClN₆O₅ : C, 63.41; H, 4.68; N, 13.44%). **12b** : (R₁ = H, R₂ = Cl) Yield 50%, m.p. 174–176 °C (Found : C, 63.34; H, 4.60; N, 13.36. Calcd. for C₃₃H₂₉ClN₆O₅ : C, 63.41; H, 4.68; N, 13.44%).

1-N-Benzylpiperazinomethyl-3-[4'-(4''-nitrobenzyloxy)-benzoylhydrazono]-5-chloroindolin-2-one (R₁ = Cl, R₂ = H) **13a** :

Yield 55%, m.p. 104–106 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 2.33–2.48 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 2.62–2.69 (4H, t, -CH₂-N(CH₂Ph)-CH₂-), 3.49 (2H, s, CH₂Ph), 4.55 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.04–7.12 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.32 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.38 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 9.0 Hz), 7.51 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.53–7.58 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.62 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 8.7 Hz), 7.85 (1H, s, Ar-H), 8.00 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 9.0 Hz), 8.27 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 8.7 Hz), 13.90 (1H, s, CONH); MS *m/z* : 638 (M⁺•), 640 (M+2) (Found : C, 63.82; H, 4.86; N, 13.18. Calcd. for C₃₄H₃₁ClN₆O₅ : C, 63.90; H, 4.89; N, 13.15%). **13b** : (R₁ = H, R₂ = Cl) Yield 50%, m.p. 210 °C (d) (Found : C, 63.82; H, 4.82; N, 13.09. Calcd. for C₃₄H₃₁ClN₆O₅ : C, 63.90; H, 4.89; N, 13.15%).

1-Dimethylaminomethyl-3-[4'-(4''-nitrobenzyloxy)-benzoylhydrazono]-5-chloroindolin-2-one (R₁ = Cl, R₂ = H) **14a** :

Yield 48%, m.p. 186–188 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3427 (NH), 2832 (>N-CH₂-N<), 1692 (CO), 1523, 1345 (NO₂), 1258 (-CH₂O-), 765 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 2.39 (6H, s, Me), 4.27 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.26 (2H, s,

-CH₂O-), 7.00–7.08 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.35 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 9.0 Hz), 7.62 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 8.7 Hz), 7.85 (1H, s, Ar-H), 8.00 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 9.0 Hz), 8.27 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 8.7 Hz), 13.98 (1H, s, CONH); MS *m/z* : 507 (M⁺•), 509 (M+2) (Found : C, 59.03; H, 4.30; N, 17.73. Calcd. for C₂₅H₂₂ClN₅O₅ : C, 59.12; H, 4.37; N, 17.79%). **14b** : (R₁ = H, R₂ = Cl) Yield 76%, m.p. 212–214 °C (Found : C, 59.00; H, 4.28; N, 17.70. Calcd. for C₂₅H₂₂ClN₅O₅ : C, 59.12; H, 4.37; N, 17.79%).

1-Diethylaminomethyl-3-[4'-(4''-nitrobenzyloxy)-benzoylhydrazono]-5-chloroindolin-2-one (R₁ = Cl, R₂ = H) **15a** :

Yield 48%, m.p. 186–188 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3427 (NH), 2832 (>N-CH₂-N<), 1692 (CO), 1523, 1345 (NO₂), 1258 (-CH₂O-), 765 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 1.98–2.10 (6H, t, Me), 2.21–2.34 (4H, q, CH₂Me), 4.47 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.26 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.00–7.08 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.35 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 9.0 Hz), 7.62 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 8.7 Hz), 7.85 (1H, s, Ar-H), 8.00 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 9.0 Hz), 8.27 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 8.7 Hz), 13.98 (1H, s, CONH); MS *m/z* : 535 (M⁺•), 537 (M+2) (Found : C, 60.42; H, 4.86; N, 13.00. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₆ClN₅O₅ : C, 60.50; H, 4.89; N, 13.07%). **15b** : (R₁ = H, R₂ = Cl) Yield 71%, m.p. 189–191 °C (Found : C, 60.45; H, 4.80; N, 13.10. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₆ClN₅O₅ : C, 60.50; H, 4.89; N, 13.07%).

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